

Use of compacted clay liner for the attenuation of landfill leachate migration from a MSW site in Durgapur, West Bengal

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Abstract : A study was undertaken to delineate the soil and ground water quality near a Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) landfill site in Durgapur, West Bengal, India. Various multivariate statistical techniques to include Pearson's correlation analysis using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 17.0) were used to assess soil quality for parameters like Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Hardness (TH), pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Calcium (Ca²⁺), Magnesium (Mg²⁺), Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Nitrate (NO₃⁻), %Total Organic Carbon (TOC), Arsenic (As) a metalloid and Heavy Metals like Chromium (Cr⁶⁺), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), Iron (Fe), Mercury (Hg), Copper (Cu), Aluminum (Al), Nickel (Ni), Zinc (Zn). Each parameter was then compared with the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) 1991 guidelines. While Pearson's Correlation Analysis was used to find out the relationship between various sampling data, Factor Analysis was applied to datasets to explain the total variance of respective datasets.

Keywords : Municipal solid waste, heavy metals, landfill leachate, statistical modeling.

I. Introduction

Municipal solid waste (MSW) in developing countries like India is disposed directly on unlined land surfaces near cities. Liner systems (barriers), the most important element in a landfill would act to isolate the solid waste and prevent contamination of the soil and groundwater by landfill leachate, the leachate generated from these sites later migrates through subsurface soil and mix with groundwater causing lithospheric pollution. The residents near the contaminated sites may face colossal health effects due to the fate of these contaminants laterally as well as vertically through the soil and groundwater and also direct or indirect consumption of polluted groundwater and due to agricultural activities in these contaminated sites.

Land filling, a preferred method of MSW disposal due to its favorable economics has been identified as one of the major threats to groundwater resources (Fatta *et al.*, 1999). Increasing recognition

is being given to pollution of soils and groundwater by municipal and industrial non-hazardous solid waste landfills, majority being sanitary landfills in which there was little or no regard given in their siting, construction, operation and closure for potential impact of leachate generated within the landfill on soil and groundwater quality. Today most pollution agencies are recommending that sanitary landfills be situated above the water table. Trace elements especially heavy metals like Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn i.e. transition metals that are of environmental concern (Batley 2012), including As. These are some of the major pollutants of the environment. Because of their toxicity, persistence and bioaccumulation problems, their occurrence in waters and biota points to the presence of natural or anthropogenic sources. Heavy metals tends to be trapped in the water and accumulate in sediments and may be directly available beneath plants or released to the water column through sediment resuspension, adsorption-desorption reac-

tion, reduction-oxidation reactions and degrading organisms. Such processes enhance the dissolved concentration of trace metals in the environment and threaten the ecosystem. Chapman (2007) defines contamination as the presence of substance where it should not be or at concentrations above background and pollution, a serious case of contamination is that which results in adverse biological effects.

Municipal landfill leachate is produced when moisture enters the refuse, extracts contaminants into the liquid phase and produces moisture content sufficiently high to initiate liquid flow. Attenuation of leachate is strongly affected by ion-exchange processes that are a function of the quantity and mineralogy of clay minerals in the surrounding materials. The rate and characteristics of leachate produced depends on many factors including, solid waste composition, particle size, degree of compaction, hydrology of site, age of landfill, moisture, temperature conditions and available oxygen. Remediation does not restore soil and groundwater quality so focus must be placed on prevention of pollution of soils and groundwater by MSW landfill leachate. Keeping these in view, the present study was undertaken to characterize the soil pollution that occurred due to release of leachate from a MSW land disposal site in Durgapur, West Bengal, India so that proper containment resisting structures can be constructed. The liner which will act as barriers to retard the spreading of the potential alarming contaminants surrounding the zone of landfill .

II. Materials and methods

A. Study area

30 year old unlined Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) landfill site located in Durgapur, West Bengal, India that has been abandoned for the past 3 years. It is identified by Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) where industrial and anthropogenic activities are concentrating and causing rigorous environmental degradation.

Fig. 1. West Bengal Map Extract 1:50,000 Sheet No. 73 M/6 showing sampling sites [Courtesy: Google Earth].

B. Sampling and analysis

The study area was divided into 5 grids A, B, C, D and E from which soil samples were collected by augur boring at predetermined depths below ground surface to study the variation of pollution levels in the subsurface. In grid A and B soil samples were collected from 15, 30 and 60 cm depths whereas in grids C and D it was collected from 20 and 40 cm below the ground surface, in grid E the soil sample was collected from 30 cm depth. A total of eleven soil samples were collected at above mentioned depths and stored in polyethylene bags before transporting to the Department of Earth and Environmental Studies, of NIT Durgapur, West Bengal, India for physico-chemical test and analysis as per the standard methods prescribed in APHA 22nd Edition : 2012. Ground water samples were collected from 12 nos. of wells, which are located in the near-by regions of the landfill area. In 2 of the wells only the DWT (depth of water table) is only noted. The location of the wells were selected on the basis of ground water flow direction. 6 nos. sample were collected from the wells located in the upstream and 5 nos. sample collected from the wells located in the downstream and 1 no. sample within the well located in between the landfill itself. 2–3 liters of water samples were collected from each well. Depth of the well is measured with the help of measuring tape. The condi-

tion of water level during the summer is recorded. The depth of water table was noted.

To generate leachate from the soil samples, 100 g of each sample was oven dried for 3 days at 60°C keeping in mind that temperatures above this would destroy biomass and minimize volatilization of some analytes (US EPA 200.2, Puget Sound). The oven dried soil samples were then pulverized by using a wooden mallet and sieved through a 425 µm sieve to form a homogenized sample as grain size plays a significant role in determining elemental concentrations in sediments.

To study the pollution levels in collected soil samples, 5 g of oven dried samples along with freshly prepared double distilled water (1 : 20) was placed into a 1000 ml capacity glass vial and rotated at 160 rpm in an orbital shaker for 24 h while maintaining the pH at 5.05 with acid buffer. The suspension was then filtered through 0.22 µm filter paper to ensure removal of organic impurities from the same thus preventing interference in analysis. The filtrate analyzed for concentration levels of respective contaminants. The procedure was repeated with distilled water of ratio 1 : 5 and shaken for 2 h without adding acid buffer and later filtered through 0.45 µm filter paper and the filtrate tested for pH, EC, and TDS.

For heavy metal analysis, to 100 g of oven dried soil sample was added 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl, 100 ml of (1 : 9) phosphoric acid, 100 ml of 0.1 N nitric acid, 200 ml of distilled water and digested for 2 h and then 50 ml of conc. HNO₃ was added to the suspension and digested for a further 30 min. The digested suspension was then transferred to 200 ml distilled water, filtered, and analyzed for Pb, Ca, Ni, Cd, Zn, Al, Hg, Cr, Fe and As. Analytical procedures are described in detail (APHA 22nd Edition : 2012-3120B).

B. Statistical method

The descriptive statistics of soil samples viz. mean, standard deviation, maximum and minimum concentrations of pollutants as exhibited in Table 3 were

calculated with SPSS 17.0 statistics software package and correlations between the parameters were assessed by using Pearson's correlation analysis. Correlation analysis is a preliminary descriptive technique of estimating the degree of association of variables to ascertain the degree of association between two variables, while in the present study Pearson's correlation analysis was used to find out the relationship between various sampling data. Factor analysis was applied to datasets to explain the total variance of respective datasets. Most parameters were found to bear significant correlation with each other indicating close association of these parameters with each other, thus a single parameter could give a reasonably good indication of a number of parameters (Vasil Simeonov, 2005).

After obtaining correlation matrix and Eigen values, factor loading was used to measure the correlation between variables and factors and then the variables were rotated by varimax rotation techniques to obtain a new set of variables which are uncorrelated and arranged in decreasing order of importance.

III. Results and discussion

A. Batch study

The mechanism of chromium attenuation was primarily attributable to adsorption by the soil as portrayed by the batch adsorption studies, the results show that the soil possess reasonably good chromium adsorption capacity at natural or slightly alkaline condition. The results of time vs different concentrations showed a variation in the amount of chromium remaining in the solution after adsorption, the percentage removal was then calculated from $[(C_o - C_e) / C_o] \times 100$ where C_o and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentration at the various times respectively, percentage removal was found to increase gradually in the initial stages before leveling off on reaching equilibrium. In almost all cases of the different concentrations, percentage removal was over 80% before stabilizing at equilibrium.

The laboratory batch adsorption test results are

Table 1. Showing percentage removal of chromium(VI) using the clayey soil used as liner material

C_o	1 h			6 h			12 h			24 h		
	C_e	%R	q_e	C_e	%R	q_e	C_e	%R	q_e	C_e	%R	q_e
0.3	0.074	75.28	56.46	0.0514	82.86	62.15	0.056	81.26	60.95	0.0531	82.30	61.73
0.5	0.124	75.25	94.063	0.0589	88.82	110.3	0.074	85.12	106.4	0.074	85.23	106.5
0.8	0.187	76.52	153.04	0.1074	86.58	173.2	0.1049	86.88	173.8	0.109	86.35	172.7
1	0.238	76.25	190.63	0.1412	85.88	214.7	0.1395	86.05	215.1	0.147	85.26	214.2

tabulated in the table below for chromium(VI) as solutes. In these experiments, the initial chromium(VI) concentration was varied from 0.3 to 1 mg/L for various at initial solution pH of 6 for a contact time 24 h. From the Table 1 it is evident that the percentage removal of chromium(VI) is highest in 6th hour in 0.5 mg/L concentration but as higher concentration is taken the removal percentage have decreased. Hence the chromium(VI) adsorption test result was obtained from the batch adsorption experimental results tabulated using soil dose of 0.4 g, adsorption dose of 0.3 to 1 mg/L maintaining pH 6.0 and contact time 24 h.

The study revealed the soils surrounding the landfill were highly contaminated with Cr^{6+} as compared to the other heavy metal ions. The high permeability value (10^{-4} cm/s) of the soil could have been the primary cause of lateral and vertical spreading of the leachate into the surrounding subsurface environment. An attempt was made in the present study to use naturally available clayey soil as primary landfill liner material to make an engineered landfill structure to impede the sub-surface migration of the contaminants from the waste disposal site. Both physical and chemical study reveals the suitability of the clay soil as liner. The low permeability value of the clay soil makes it more suitable to be used as liner material. The detail of the physical and chemical analysis are illustrated below in Table 6. Laboratory scale batch adsorption studies were carried out with synthetically prepared Cr^{6+} solution as test contaminant and clay soil as adsorbent. The study revealed high Cr^{6+} adsorption capacity of clay soil. The batch adsorption study for Cr^{6+} by the clayey soil used as liner material was done and the linear isotherm model

provided a best fit ($R^2 = 0.95$, RMSE = 8.01) to give a partition coefficient (K_d) for Cr^{6+} of 15559.4 L/kg. Freundlich adsorption models were fitted to the test results and the relevant isotherm parameters of model were obtained as ($K_f = 1.864$ L/kg, $1/n = 1.0778$ and $R^2 = 0.89$) with $1/n$ corresponding to high adsorptive intensity implicating that the retardation factor was relatively high and the soil had high Cr^{6+} attenuation capacity, in addition the Langmuir model parameters as ($Q_{max} = 6.66$ mg/g and $b = 1.875$ L/mg, $R^2 = 0.83$, RMSE = 16.73) indicating that the maximum amount of Cr^{6+} that could be adsorbed was 6.66 mg/g reflecting the soil as having relatively high Cr^{6+} adsorption capacity at natural mean *in situ* pH condition of about 7.

Descriptive statistics for background pollutants concentrations in soil samples were presented in Table 3, which indicated a wide variation of As (1.05–0.48), Cd (0.48–0.23), Pb (8.65–2.33), Fe (11413–4733), Hg (0.24–0.09), Cr (12.5–6.43), Cu (10.93–2.18), Al (13333–4657), Ni (7.90–3.80) and Zn (50.70–2.35) mg kg^{-1} . The results revealed that the amount of heavy metals depend on the sampling locations. To determine the extent of enrichment of heavy metals in the soils, concentrations obtained were compared with CCME (1991) standards. Ex-

Table 2. Linear, Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm constants, R^2 and RMSE values for chromium(VI) adsorption on clay soil

Models	Isotherm constants	R^2	RMSE
Linear	$K_d = 1559.4$ L/kg	0.95	8.01
Freundlich	$K_F = 1.864$ L/kg $1/n = 1.0778$	0.89	8.58
Langmuir	$Q_{max} = 6.66$ mg/g $b = 1.875$ L/mg	0.83	16.73

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of soil samples collected from landfill [heavy metal concentrations] in mg kg⁻¹, other units in ppm except pH and EC (µS/cm)

	%TOC	pH	EC	TDS	NO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	TH	Zn	As	Cd	Pb	Fe	Hg	Cr	Cu	Al	Ni
Mean	1.50	6.72	1166.8	29.4	37.31	259.77	332.8	46.48	800.0	18.29	0.74	0.38	4.6	8010	0.14	10.16	5.80	7336	5.02
SD	0.75	0.69	827.2	20.7	21.17	136.19	277.7	36.82	829.5	19.30	0.23	0.09	2.37	2747	0.06	2.91	3.25	3603	1.69
Max	2.60	7.75	2576.0	64.4	53.98	496.48	768.0	96.00	2240	50.70	1.05	0.48	8.65	11413	0.24	12.50	10.93	13333	7.90
Min	0.78	6.13	514.0	12.8	12.82	169.42	96.0	2.00	60	2.35	0.48	0.23	2.33	4733	0.09	6.43	2.18	4657	3.80
Threshold	-	6-8	2000	-	-	50	75	30	-	200	12	1.4	70	-	6.6	1.4	63	-	50

Table 4. Correlation coefficient matrix of parameters of MSW landfill soils

	TOC	pH	EC	TDS	NO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	TH	As	Cd	Pb	Fe	Hg	Cr	Cu	Al	Ni	Zn
TOC	1																		
pH	0.893	1																	
EC	0.956	0.905	1																
TDS	0.957	0.903	1	1															
NO ₃ ⁻	0.853	0.625	0.677	0.681	1														
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.820	0.756	0.944	0.944	0.477	1													
Ca ²⁺	0.549	0.630	0.762	0.759	0.133	0.900	1												
Mg ²⁺	0.981	0.814	0.901	0.903	0.887	0.748	0.414	1											
TH	0.905	0.818	0.976	0.976	0.586	0.963	0.770	0.870	1										
As	-0.481	-0.806	-0.480	-0.480	-0.251	-0.292	-0.329	-0.377	-0.352	1									
Cd	0.164	0.062	0.395	0.395	-0.138	0.675	0.777	0.096	0.505	0.328	1								
Pb	0.685	0.627	0.855	0.855	0.289	0.973	0.918	0.616	0.917	-0.171	0.794	1							
Fe	-0.614	-0.711	-0.499	-0.499	-0.493	-0.230	0.015	-0.645	-0.450	0.727	0.495	-0.114	1						
Hg	-0.690	-0.584	-0.555	-0.555	-0.629	-0.326	0.050	-0.783	-0.568	0.373	0.312	-0.235	0.891	1					
Cr	-0.761	-0.878	-0.648	-0.648	-0.685	-0.377	-0.192	-0.728	-0.516	0.859	0.418	-0.195	0.876	0.696	1				
Cu	0.658	0.528	0.815	0.815	0.332	0.955	0.884	0.600	0.879	-0.015	0.849	0.980	0.023	-0.158	-0.090	1			
Al	-0.607	-0.529	-0.481	-0.481	-0.527	-0.258	0.098	-0.705	-0.507	0.369	0.344	-0.186	0.899	0.992	0.655	-0.10	1		
Ni	-0.652	-0.533	-0.512	-0.512	-0.606	-0.285	0.096	-0.755	-0.532	0.326	0.326	-0.201	0.874	0.998	0.657	-0.13	0.99	1	
Zn	0.862	0.717	0.937	0.937	0.563	0.954	0.742	0.846	0.987	-0.199	0.579	0.929	-0.359	-0.544	-0.395	0.91	-0.48	-0.52	1

Table 5. Correlation coefficient matrix of parameters of ground water samples

	pH	EC (ppm)	TDS (μ s)	NO_3^- (ppm)	SO_4^{2-} (mg/L)	Ca^{2+} (mg/L)	Mg^{2+} (mg/L)	TH (mg/L)	Cu (mg/L)	Cr (mg/L)	Pb (mg/L)	Fe (mg/L)	Zn (mg/L)
pH	1												
EC	-0.14349	1											
(ppm)													
TDS	-0.11116	0.988838	1										
(μ s)													
NO_3^-	-0.26744	0.461761	0.482959	1									
(ppm)													
SO_4^{2-}	0.13995	0.291357	0.317403	0.55225	1								
(mg/L)													
Ca^{2+}	0.366537	0.324114	0.365392	0.44441	0.79392533	1							
(mg/L)													
Mg^{2+}	-0.40713	0.741619	0.747707	0.63538	0.49947172	0.373662861	1						
(mg/L)													
TH	0.11895	0.55264	0.58709	0.6020	0.8180696	0.92630470	0.695605	1					
(mg/L)													
Cu	0	3.33E-17	4.32E-17	-3E-16	1.4905E-16	-1.9818E-16	0	0	1				
(mg/L)													
Cr	0	3.33E-17	4.32E-17	-3E-16	1.4905E-16	-1.9818E-16	0	0	1	1			
(mg/L)													
Pb	0	3.33E-17	4.32E-17	-3E-16	1.4905E-16	-1.9818E-16	0	0	1	1	1		
(mg/L)													
Fe	0.33599	0.14898	0.13756	-0.3328	0.2887375	0.16843209	0.1877608	0.2070491	2.6E-16	2.6E-16	2.6E-16	1	
(mg/L)													
Zn	0.19233	0.13091	0.1091	0.2933	0.4781946	0.77824318	0.1390415	0.6588869	6.8E-2	6.8E-2	6.8E-2	0.0691	1
(mg/L)													

Table 6. Physico-chemical properties selected as liner material

Properties	Test results
Specific gravity	2.34
Dry density at ODD (g/cc)	1.76
Optimum moisture content (%)	15.9
CBR value	1.72
Liquid limit	38.5
Plastic limit	23.8
Plasticity index	14.7
pH	7.70
EC (ppm)	338
TDS	660
Chromium (ppm)	Nil
Permeability (cm/s)	6.5×10^{-7}

cept for Cr, the arithmetic mean of Fe, Al, Zn, Cu, Ni, Pb, Cd and As were below the threshold value of background. Noticeably the average concentration of Cr was approximately 7 times more than its background value, clearly indicating that the study area was highly contaminated with Cr. The relationship between heavy metals could provide important information on heavy metal sources and pathways (Wei *et al.*, 2009) in the study area. Pearson's correlation coefficients and their significance in the soils were summarized in Table 4. Significant positive correlations existed between Al-Ni, Cu-Zn, Hg-Ni, Fe-Al, Pb-Cu, Pb-Zn, Cd-Cu, and As-Cr pairs stating a probable common source of the couples. Pearson's correlation coefficients and their significance in the ground water were summarized in Table 5. Significant positive correlations existed between EC-TDS, EC-Mg²⁺, TDS-Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺-Zn, SO₂-Ca²⁺, SO₂-TH, Ca²⁺-TH.

Adsorption study of chromium(VI) was conducted and it results to 80–88% removal of chromium(VI) was observed within (6–8) hour of adsorption. Therefore desorption study was conducted to extract the amount of chromium(VI) absorbed in the liner material. Test results showed only (10–15%) desorption of chromium from the soil, Therefore to reinforce this statement, a SEM analysis was performed for the raw soil and the soil absorbing synthetic

chromium(VI) solution (after performing the adsorption study). SEM analysis is performed to study the chemical absorption of the chromium(VI) in the soil because while performing the desorption study only 10% of chromium(VI) is extracted while removal percentage is above 88% (approx.). Therefore, the pictures shown in Figs. 2 and 3 clearly shows difference in Fig. 2 the raw soil structures has completely changed the flakes that are visible in Fig. 3 are the chromium(VI) which are in quite high amount.

Fig. 2. SEM analysis of raw soil.

Fig. 3. SEM analysis of chromium contaminated soil.

IV. Conclusion

The groundwater quality data and soil quality revealed that an alarming level of concern in the surrounding aquifer zone. Analysis of soil quality in the study area reveals that the chromium concentration (12.5 mg/kg) exceeded the prescribed limit of CCME (1991) standard specification (1.4 mg/kg). A low cost, locally available fine grained clay soil were tested for suitability of using as liner material for containment of chromium waste migration to the sub-surface aquifer. Based on present study and fitting of experimental data on various models. As there was no natural or other possible reason for high concentration of these pollutants, it was concluded that leachate had significant impact on soil quality around the MSW landfill site. The present study has also shown that the soils within this area are contaminated mainly by Cr which can be considered a menace to the residents who daily intake planted vegetables and food crops from within this area and its proximities. The study also highlighted the need for further research and regular monitoring, in order to

determine the permitted levels of pollutants in the study area and its proximities.

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